

Lanthanide(III) complexes of *N*-arylthioureas

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Lanthanide(III) complexes of the general formula, $[LnX_{3-m}(Ptu)_n]X_m \cdot 2H_2O$ and $[LnX_{3-m}(o/m/p-Totu)_n]X_m \cdot 2H_2O$ [where, Ln = Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, Y; X = NO₃, Cl; Ptui = *N*-phenylthiourea, Totu = tolylthiourea; *m* = 0, 1 and *n* = 3, 4] have been isolated and characterized. A few complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes while others are non-electrolytic in nature. Sulphur of the ligands takes part in coordination to the central metal ion. The electronic spectra have been analyzed and spectral parameters calculated. Higher coordination number of six, seven and eight exhibited by some of the complexes is the characteristic feature of lanthanides.

In the last few years there has been a renewed interest in lanthanide(III) complexes with high coordination number¹. The lanthanides are known to form weak complexes with sulphur ligands such as thioureas which is partly due to the larger ionic radii of the metal ions and the lower electronegativity of sulphur atom. We and others² have earlier investigated the transition metal complexes of *N*- and *N,N'*-disubstituted-thioureas. However, the reports on lanthanide complexes of thioureas is scanty³. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of complexes derived from *N*-arylthioureas like *N*-phenylthiourea (Ptui) and *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-tolylthiourea (Totu) with the first series lanthanide metal ions.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in methanol. The molar conductance values in MeOH (Table 1) indicate that a few complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytic in nature (59–100 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ at 10⁻³ M concentration) while some are non-electrolyte (8–46 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in the above solvent⁴. The paramagnetic behaviour of lanthanide(III) ions is consistent with the presence of unpaired 4*f*-electrons. Since these electrons are well shielded by ⁵S₂ ⁵P₆ octet both in their spin and orbital motion, the magnetic moment of a complex should indicate whether these 4*f*-electrons take part in bond formation or not. The room temperature magnetic moments of the present lanthanide(III) complexes show little deviation from the Van Vleck values⁵, indicating no significant participation of 4*f*-electrons in bond formation. However, in case of the samarium(III) complexes, the magnetic moment values are found to be slightly more than Van Vleck's values. This may presumably be due to temperature-dependent magnetism on account of low *J*-separation⁶. In other words, the energy difference between the ground state level (⁶H_{5/2}) and the next higher *J*-level (⁶H_{7/2}) being only of the order

of *kT*, leads to population of the higher energy levels and susceptibilities due to first-order Zeeman effect⁷.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the complexes*

Compd. no.	Complex/ (Colour)	Metal % : Found / (Calcd)	λ _m Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B M
1	[PrCl ₂ (Ptui) ₄]Cl·2H ₂ O (Green)	15.83 (15.79)	99.4	3.53
2	[PrCl ₂ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄]Cl·2H ₂ O (Green)	14.56 (14.86)	89.2	3.53
3	Pr(NO ₃) ₃ (Ptui) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pale green)	17.37 (17.19)	44.8	3.20
4	Pr(NO ₃) ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pale green)	16.34 (16.35)	46.9	3.25
5	NdCl ₃ (Ptui) ₄ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	19.24 (19.41)	58.1	3.22
6	NdCl ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	18.32 (18.37)	59.1	3.56
7	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ (Ptui) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	17.56 (17.53)	38.7	3.38
8	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pink)	16.40 (16.68)	44.4	3.45
9	[Sm(NO ₃) ₂ (Ptui) ₄]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Colourless)	15.16 (15.32)	89.6	2.04
10	[Sm(NO ₃) ₂ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Colourless)	14.24 (14.49)	88.3	2.21
11	Sm(NO ₃) ₃ (<i>m</i> -Totu) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Pale yellow)	17.20 (17.26)	58.5	1.94
12	[Sm(NO ₃) ₂ (<i>p</i> -Totu) ₆]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Colourless)	10.76 (10.98)	88.7	1.88
13	EuCl ₃ (Ptui) ₃ ·2H ₂ O (Yellow)	20.32 (20.24)	8.3	3.32
14	EuCl ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄ ·2H ₂ O (Yellow)	15.81 (15.84)	11.5	3.37

*Since deceased.

Table-1 (contd.)

15	DyCl ₃ (Ptu) ₅ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	15.18 (15.25)	11.3	9.53
16	DyCl ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	16.49 (16.76)	10.4	10.13
17	[Ho(NO ₃) ₂ (Ptu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	16.68 (16.56)	84.6	10.68
18	[Ho(NO ₃) ₂ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	15.74 (15.68)	94.4	10.65
19	ErCl ₃ (Ptu) ₃ .2H ₂ O (Pink)	21.45 (21.83)	52.0	9.60
20	ErCl ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₃ .2H ₂ O (Pink)	20.57 (20.69)	51.5	9.76
21	[Er(NO ₃) ₂ (Ptu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Pale pink)	16.86 (16.76)	93.3	9.71
22	[Er(NO ₃) ₂ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Pink)	15.81 (15.87)	89.8	9.66
23	[Yb(NO ₃) ₂ (Ptu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	14.94 (14.97)	88.2	4.63
24	[Yb(NO ₃) ₂ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₄]NO ₃ .2H ₂ O (Colourless)	16.29 (16.32)	93.3	4.82
25	[Y(NO ₃) ₃ (Ptu) ₃].2H ₂ O (Colourless)	11.50 (11.58)	6.9	Dia
26	[Yb(NO ₃) ₃ (<i>o</i> -Totu) ₃].2H ₂ O (Colourless)	10.93 (10.98)	6.8	Dia

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

The assignments of different bands in the ir spectra of compounds were made as per the procedure suggested by Jensen and Nielsen⁸. The absence of splitting in NH band (3400–3200 cm⁻¹) and a slight high frequency shift in the NH₂ band (1620 cm⁻¹) in case of the complexes reveal that nitrogen of NH₂ group does not participate in coordination. A strong band at 1520 cm⁻¹ (ν asy NCN + δ NH₂) shifts slightly to higher frequencies indicating the increased double bond character of C–N. No marked shift is observed for a composite band at 1100 cm⁻¹ but a decrease in intensity of this band may be due to equal contribution of ν sym NCN + ν CS. The bands observed at 760 and 670 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν CS + ν CN and ν CS respectively. A low frequency shift of 2–10 cm⁻¹ with reduction in intensity of these two bands indicates that sulphur is involved in coordination. The far-ir spectral bands at 350 cm⁻¹ due to M–S vibration also supports sulphur coordination^{9,10}. The M–Cl band appears at 280 cm⁻¹. The lanthanide(III) nitrate complexes of *N*-arylthioureas exhibit medium intensity bands at 1460, 1380, 1010, 820, 720 and 710 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to the ν_4 , ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_6 , ν_3 and ν_5 frequencies of the coordinated nitrate (C_{2v}) groups¹¹. However, bands at 840 and 1390 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) group which is also confirmed by conductance data. Thus, a few lanthanide complexes have both ionic and coordinated nitrate groups. Further, the difference ν_1 – ν_4 of 70–90 cm⁻¹ confirms the monodentate nature of the nitrate group in the corresponding lanthanide complexes. Finally, a broad band appearing in the spectra of all complexes at 3500–3550 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the presence of water of hydration¹⁰.

The visible spectral data for the Nd, Pr, Sm, Ho and Er complexes are reported in Table 2. Generally, the *f*–*f* transi-

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of complexes

Compd. no.	Assign-ment	Ln ³⁺ ion	λ_{max} (×10 ³ cm ⁻¹)	Complex	β'	Other parameters	<i>f</i> ×10 ⁻³					
2 (3)	³ P ₂ – ³ H ₄	22.54	22.44	22.46	0.9956	$\beta'_{av} = 0.9969$ (0.9956)	14.12					
								³ P ₁ –	21.35	21.26	0.9958	$\delta = 0.3110$ (0.4419)
									³ P ₀ –	20.76	20.71	0.9980
5 (6)	² G _{9/2} – ⁴ I _{9/2}	19.5	19.56	1.0008	$\beta'_{av} = 0.9941$ (0.9935)	18.69						
							⁴ G _{7/2} –	19.12	19.10	0.9954	$\delta = 0.5935$ (0.6543)	
								² G _{7/2} –	17.34	17.18	0.9876	$b^{1/2} = 0.0543$ (0.0570)
9 (10)	⁶ P _{3/2} – ⁶ H _{5/2}	26.71	26.66	0.9984	$\beta'_{av} = 0.9977$ (0.9984)	13.48						
							⁴ F _{9/2} –	25.00	24.77	0.9911	$\delta = 0.2305$ (0.1603)	
								⁴ P _{5/2} –	24.06	23.99	0.9971	$b^{1/2} = 0.0339$ (0.0283)
17 (18)	⁵ G ₆ – ⁵ I ₈	24.09	23.99	0.9957	$\beta'_{av} = 0.9983$ (0.9987)	18.49						
							⁵ G ₅ –	22.16	22.20	1.0018	$\delta = 0.1703$ (0.1302)	
								⁵ F ₁ –	21.38	21.36	0.9992	$b^{1/2} = 0.0292$ (0.0255)
20 (21)	⁴ G _{11/2} – ⁴ I _{15/2}	27.47	27.44	0.9989	$\beta'_{av} = 0.9994$ (0.9996)	28.72						
							⁴ F _{7/2} –	26.40	26.37	0.9989	$\delta = 0.060$ (0.040)	
								² H _{11/2} –	20.54	20.53	0.9995	$b^{1/2} = 0.0173$ (0.0141)
	⁴ S _{3/2} –	19.14	19.13	0.9995								
							⁴ F _{9/2} –	15.33	15.33	1.0000		

tions are slightly affected by the immediate surrounding of the lanthanide cation and this is commonly attributed to the

'buried' or shielded nature of the 4*f*-orbitals by the overlying ⁵S₂ and ⁵P₆ shells. However, shift to longer wavelength, splitting and enhancement of certain bands can be observed on complex formation¹². The nephelauxetic effect is in fact correlated with the covalency of the metal-ligand bonding and the Sinha's parameter (δ) is usually taken as a measure of covalency¹³,

$$\delta = \left(\frac{1 - \beta}{\beta} \right) \times 100$$

where, β is the average value of the ratio of complex/aquo ion. The absorption spectra of the Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes show appreciable shift to lower frequency with respect to the aquo-ion as stated in Table 2. The δ values observed for the Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes are relatively smaller (0.04–0.23) than that observed for the Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes (0.3–0.65). All the average values of β' and δ are however positive, but smaller than unity which indicate weak covalent bonding. The bonding parameter, $b^{1/2}$, the magnitude of which suggests the comparative involvement of the 4*f*-orbital metal-ligand bond, is related to the nephelauxetic ratio β' by the expression¹⁴,

$$b^{1/2} = \left(\frac{1 - \beta}{2} \right)^{1/2}$$

The positive values of bonding parameter (0.014–0.057) is indicative of covalent character in the metal-ligand bond in phenylthiourea complexes. The absorption intensities, presented as oscillator strength, were calculated from the expression¹⁵,

$$f = (4.6 \times 10^{-9}) \epsilon_{\max} \Delta\nu_{1/2}$$

where, ϵ_{\max} is molecular absorptivity of the peak maximum and $\nu_{1/2}$ is half-band width. The low intensity of the bands (oscillator strength 10⁻³) suggests that all bands are due to forbidden electric dipole transitions which occur between ground state and excited state of the *fⁿ*-configuration¹⁶.

Table 3. Thermal data of lanthanide complexes with *N*-arylthioureas

Compd. no.	Dec. temp. °C	% Wt loss		Nature of decomposition
		obs	(Calcd.)	
2	119	3.50	3.80	Loss of two H ₂ O
	284	16.00	15.02	Loss of 2H ₂ O + 3Cl
6	103	4.50	4.59	Loss of two H ₂ O
	204	13.62	13.49	Loss of 2Cl + 2H ₂ O
12	104	2.50	2.62	Loss of two H ₂ O
	480	41.80	43.5	Loss of 2H ₂ O + 1NO ₃ + 1 <i>p</i> -Totu
18	103	3.50	3.55	Loss of two H ₂ O
	544	46.50	46.82	Loss of 2H ₂ O + 2NO ₃ + 2 <i>o</i> -Totu
21	101	3.50	3.61	Loss of two H ₂ O
	274	17.00	16.02	Loss of 2H ₂ O + 2NO ₃
23	106	3.00	3.12	Loss of two H ₂ O
	428	33.0	34.8	Loss of 2H ₂ O + NO ₃ + 2 Ptu

The thermal analysis of thiourea complexes indicates the loss of all water molecules in one step at 110° which confirms the presence of non-coordinated water. In the subsequent step further loss in weight of the complex in the temperature range 160–400° was observed corresponding to the loss of anions and ligand. These results (Table 3) are in agreement with that obtained from the chemical analysis regarding the composition of the complex.

Thus on the basis of the analytical and spectral data discussed above, the following structures are proposed for the lanthanide complexes of Ptu and Totu.

Experimental

Lanthanide(III) oxides (99.9% pure) were obtained from Koch-Light and Indian Rare Earths Ltd. Phenylthiourea and tolythiourea were prepared by the reported method¹⁷. Solvents were dried and freshly distilled prior to use. Hydrated lanthanide(III) chloride/nitrate was obtained by dissolving the oxide in dilute HCl or HNO₃ and evaporating the excess acid. A mixture of hydrated lanthanide chloride/nitrate (1 mmol) and the thiourea (3 mmol) dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 ml), was refluxed for longer period until turbidity appeared (15–25 h). Then the solution was concentrated to a small volume and the mass was extracted with petroleum ether (50 ml; 40–60°). It was stirred for 30 min, washed with a mixture of ethanol and petroleum ether (1 : 1) and finally dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅.

Lanthanide metal was estimated gravimetrically as its oxinate¹⁸. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method; S and Cl gravimetrically as BaSO₄ and AgCl respectively¹⁹. C and H were estimated by microanalytical method. Conductivity was measured using an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. The magnetic moment at room temperature (27 ± 1°) was determined on Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Hitachi 270 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer. TG studies were carried out in the 25–600° range on a Stanton Redcraft balance at a heating rate of 20° min⁻¹ in static air.

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